

PERCEIVED EXERTION OF 8TH AND 9TH STANDARD SCHOOL GOING CHILDREN WHILE CARRYING BACKPACKSJayshree Rodge¹, Swati Gaikwad² and Swati Suryavanshi³

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Abstract

The present study entitled “perceived exertion of 8th and 9th standard school going children while carrying backpacks.” was undertaken by conducting survey among forty high going boys and girls between 13- 15 yrs. age who were using backpacks. Twenty boys and 20 girls each studying in high school 8th and 9th standards from different schools of Parbhani town were selected for this study. The finding revealed that majority of boys and girls of 8th and 9th standards sometime felt their backpacks were heavy. Majority of boys and girls of 8th standard felt that carrying school backpack were moderately exerting while majority boys of 9th standard felt carrying backpack were moderately exerting and girls of 9th standard felt it was very exerting while carrying school backpack. Weight of 8th and 9th standards girls were positively correlated with perceived exertion and BMI of 9th standards girls was positively correlated with perceived exertion because of increased weight and BMI girls felt exerted while carrying a backpack.

Key words: Perceived exertion, Backpacks, School going children**Introduction:**

Students and backpacks are a common sight today. Backpacks come in a variety of sizes, colours, materials, and shapes and they enable children of all ages to express their individual style. Many backpacks have several compartments to keep students organized while they transport their books and papers from home to school or their body frames. Students of all ages hold a school bag containing textbooks, notebooks, library books, geometrical and numerical instruments, and other materials. The backpack is one of the several forms of manual load carriage that provides versatility and often used by hikers ‘backpackers, soldiers, as well as by school Children (Knapik et al 1996).

The integration of the user and backpack is a study of ergonomics based on anthropometrics and biomechanics. Throughout the world million of students can be seen heading of school with heavy backpack. India is a country to a population of about 1205.6 million, (Census 2011) of which 19.61 % comprises of adolescent (10 -19 years) children they use to stuff backpack with books, copies, water bottle, tiffin and other miscellaneous items such as umbrella, purse, geometry box etc. This academic load that they carry is now viewed as a considerable daily occupational load for school going children. (Nergini 1999).

Postural discomfort is a condition in which there is pain in the lower back but no major tissue injury or trauma. Patients with postural discomfort only feel a dull ache or a sharp pain when they engage in activities that put sustained stress on normal tissue (Lockhart et al. 2004). It is feared that overloaded schoolbags, which are up to twice the size of those borne ten years ago, are contributing to the increase. Because children's skeletons are still developing, carrying

Rating of workload perception

Sr. No.	Scale	Score
1	Very Heavy	5
2	Heavy	4
3	Moderately Heavy	3
4	Light	2
5	Very Light	1

Assessment of perceived load

Information on perceived load experienced by selected 8th and 9th standard boys and girls was collected on three point scale as always, some times and never with respective score of 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

Correlation Co-efficient

Correlation co-efficient was calculated for describing the degree of correlation between dependent and independent variables in the study were age, weight, and BMI of selected 8th and 9th standards

heavy bags can cause long-term damage.' Many people wear their bags on one shoulder or arm, and gradually on the crook of their elbow, putting a lot of pressure on their spine (Mackie et al.2005).

Objective: To assess the exertion perceived by selected school going children while carrying backpacks.

Materials and Methods**Selection of the Sample**

The present study was carried out in the Parbhani town of Marathwada region in Maharashtra state. Twenty Boys and 20 girls studying in 8th and 9th standard, aged between 13-15 yrs. were selected from different schools of Parbhani town.

Equipments used for collecting data:

Weighing machine 2) Anthrop meter 3) Measuring tape

Method of data collection

The study was conducted by survey to find out information of 8th and 9th standard school going students and asking them question through questionnaire regarding perceived exertion while carrying school backpacks.

Body mass index (BMI) was calculated by using the following formula

$$\text{BMI (kg/m}^2\text{)} = \frac{\text{Weight (Kg)}}{\text{Height (m)}^2}$$

Perceived exertion of selected high school going students while carrying school backpack**Assessment of rate of perceived exertion**

A modified perceived exertion five point scales has been developed by Varghese et al. (1994) was used in the Present study: The scale is mentioned below:

school going students. Correlation co-efficient was calculated by using the following formula

$$r(x, y) = \frac{\text{Covariance (X,Y)}}{\sqrt{\text{Variance (x). Variance (y)}}$$

‘t’ test

‘t’ test was used to find out the mean differences in variables. Following formula was used to assess ‘t’ value (Sharma 2005)

$$t = \frac{M_1 - M_2}{\sqrt{\frac{(SD_1)^2 + (SD_2)^2}{n}}}$$

Results and Discussion

Table No.1 depicts the perceived feeling of heaviness of the backpack by the students while carrying to school. It was found that majority of (80% and 70%) of 8th standard boys and girls sometimes felt their backpack heavy followed by 10 per cent boys and 20 per cent girls always felt their backpack heavy, whereas equal percentages (10%) of boys and girls never felt their backpacks were heavy.

With respect to 9th standard students, majority and equal percentage (60%) of them sometimes felt their backpack heavy, followed by 40 per cent boys and 60 per cent girls always felt their backpack heavy and only 20 per cent boys and 10 per cent girls never felt their backpack heavy. It concluded that majority of boys and girls of 8th and 9th standard sometimes felt their backpacks were heavy.

The information regarding the mean score of perceived exertion and level of exertion experienced by the selected 8th and 9th standard school going students while carrying a backpack is presented in table 2. This table indicates that majority of boys and girls (50% and 60% respectively) of 8th standard were moderately exerted while carrying school backpack, followed by 30 per cent boys were comfortable and 20 per cent girls were very exerted while carrying school backpack.

Majority of the (50%) 9th standard boys were moderately exerted while carrying school backpack, followed by an equal percentage (20%) were expressed very exerted and comfortable and 10 per cent expressed that they were moderately comfortable while carrying school backpack. As regards the girls, it was noticed that majority (50%) of them were very exerted while carrying school backpack, followed by 20 per cent were comfortable and an equal percentage (10%) were moderately exerted and moderately comfortable.

Comparison between perceived exertion of selected high school going students while carrying a backpack is presented in table 3. It is evident from the table that the mean perceived exertion values of 8th & 9th standard boys were less than the girls of 8th & 9th standard but calculated 't' values showed non-significant results.

Correlation between independent variables and perceived exertion of selected high school going students while carrying backpacks is presented in table 4. It is evident from the table that selected independent variables such as age, weight, and BMI of boys of selected 8th, 9th standard showed a non-significant correlation with perceived exertion, whereas weight (0.664*) and BMI (0.611*) of 8th

standard girls were positively correlated with perceived exertion. This indicates that as the weight, and BMI of 8th standard girls increased there was an increase in perceived exertion. Body weight (0.607*) of 9th standard girls showed a positive correlation with perceived exertion, indicating that as the weight of 9th standard girls increased there perceived exertion increased.

Conclusion

It is concluded that majority of boys and girls of 8th and 9th standard sometime felt their backpacks were heavy. Majority of boys and girls of 8th standard felt that carrying school backpack were moderately exerting while majority boys of 9th standard felt carrying backpack were moderately exerting and girls of 9th standards felt it was very exerting while carrying school backpack. Weight of 8th and 9th standard girls were positively correlated with perceived exertion and BMI of 9th standard girls was positively correlated with perceived exertion. Because of increased weight and BMI girls felt exerted while carrying a backpack.

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Table 1 The perceived feeling of heaviness of the backpack by the studentswhile carrying to school

Perceived Load	Standard			
	8 th		9 th	
	Boys (N= 10)	Girls (N= 10)	Boys (N=10)	Boys (N= 10)
Always	1 (10)	2 (20)	4(40)	6(60)
Sometimes	8(80)	7(70)	6(60)	6(60)
Never	1(10)	1(10)	2(20)	1(10)

Figures in parenthesis indicate percentages

Table 2 Mean score of perceived exertion and level of exertion experienced by the selected high school going students while carrying a school backpack

Standard	Meanscore	Frequency and percentage				
		Very exerting	Moderately Exerting	Comfortable	Moderately comfortable	Most Comfortable
8 th standard						
1) Boys (N=10)	3.6	1 (10)	5 (50)	3 (30)	1 (10)	---
2) Girls (N=10)	3.9	2 (20)	6 (60)	1 (10)	1 (10)	---
9 th standard						
1) Boys (N=10)	3.8	2 (20)	5 (50)	2 (20)	1 (10)	---
2) Girls (N=10)	4.1	5 (50)	2 (10)	2 (20)	1 (10)	---

Figures in parenthesis indicate percentage

Table 3 Comparison between perceived exertion of selected high school going students while carrying school backpack

Standard	Boys	Girls	't' value
8 th standard	3.6 ± 0.843	3.9 ± 0.85	0.885 ^{NS}
9 th standard	3.8 ± 0.918	4.1 ± 1.1	0.663 ^{NS}

NS – Non Significant,

Table 4 Correlation between independent variables and perceived exertion of selected high school going students while carrying a school backpack

Variables	Class of studying			
	Boys		Girls	
	8 th (N=10)	9 th (N=10)	8 th (N=10)	9 th (N=10)
Age	0.375 ^{NS}	0.333 ^{NS}	0.133 ^{NS}	0.243 ^{NS}
Weight	0.388 ^{NS}	0.202 ^{NS}	0.664*	0.607*
BMI	0.554 ^{NS}	0.26 ^{NS}	0.611*	0.576 ^{NS}

NS – Non Significant,

* - Significant at 5% level